

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D5.3 TraceMyFish Data Platform v2.0

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D5.3
DELIVERABLE TITLE	TraceMyFish Data Platform v2.0
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TraceMyFish is part of the ERA-NET Cofund BlueBio with funding provided by national sources [i.e., General Secretariat for Research and Innovation in Greece, Research Council of Norway, Innovation Fund Denmark and Icelandic Centre for Research in Iceland] and co-funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, Grant Agreement number 817992.

PROJECT ACRONYM	TraceMyFish
PROJECT FULL NAME	Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain
STARTING DATE (DUR.)	01/11/2021 (24 months)
ENDING DATE	31/10/2023
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WORKPACKAGE N. TITLE	WP5 TraceMyFish data ecosystem
WORKPACKAGE LEADER	SCiO
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DATE OF DELIVERY (CONTRACTUAL)	31/10/2023
DATE OF DELIVERY (SUBMITTED)	15/11/2023
VERSION STATUS	1.0
NATURE	DEMONSTRATOR
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PUBLIC
AUTHORS (PARTNER)	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
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VERSION	MODIFICATION(S)	DATE	AUTHOR(S)
v0.1	ToC	15.09.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.2	Architectural specification section	01.10.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.6	Technologies description section	01.10.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.8	Full draft	15.10.2023	Antonis Koukourikos (SCiO)
v0.9	Internal review	01.11.2023	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)
v1.0	Document finalisation and submission	15.11.2023	Panagiotis Zervas (SCiO)

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ACRONYMS LIST

API	Application Programming Interface
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
IoT	Internet-of-Things
CSV	Comma-separated Values (document)
REST	Representational State Transfer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report provides an overview of the TraceMyFish Data Platform and the respective architectural and technical choices for implementing it. The drivers for defining the platform were the general requirements for the envisioned iFMS, the sensing solutions defined in the context of WP3, the data specifications as elicited from the relevant work on WP2 of the project, *Tracking hazards & potential measures*, and the nature and structure of data generated from the TraceMyFish pilots in the context of WP6, *Piloting and Evaluation*.

Within the report, the finalised architecture for the TraceMyFish data platform and its main components is presented and described, while the technologies and frameworks comprising the TraceMyFish software stack are specified. The core infrastructural elements of the platform were established and made operational earlier on the project. The main development with respect to the previous version of the report is the implementation of the **TraceMyFish app**, a web application that allows users to register their product sample measurements and invoke the predictive models developed in WP4 to acquire the predicted values for the different cases covered by the pilot cases. The report describes the app workflow and its connection with the overall platform.

1 INTRODUCTION

TraceMyFish aims to advance supply system in three geographically distributed blue bioeconomy value chains, by designing and implementing an iFish Management System (iFMS) that will allow the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains. Moreover, the TraceMyFish iFMS will establish a secure, trust-enabled data infrastructure, which will collect, pre-process and analyse data coming from innovative, portable sensing devices of different nature and modality (spectral imaging, variegating IoT sensors) and informing specialized AI models and architecture that will enable timely risk prediction to different value chain actors. The examined fish products will carry smart barcodes that, in communication with the iFMS, will carry safety information related to each product and will allow stakeholders and consumers to easily and reliably access this information at any time.

Towards this objective, data management and analysis are crucial for the accurate, timely and secure production and presentation of insights to the users at different stages of the value chain, via easy-to-use interfaces. In this context, WP5 aims to put in place the infrastructure that will realise the data storage and analytics functions required by the platform, develop, train and deploy the AI components that will power the recommendation and decision support features, and build the user-facing applications that will provide access to the data collected throughout the targeted value chains along with the recommendations to the human monitoring a given value chain link.

Building on the architectural specification reported in the relevant D5.1 deliverable, D5.2 presents the adaptation on the initial specification based on the outcomes of the project and the refined requirements. It reports on the technologies used and their organisation and communication mechanisms. In more detail, Section 2 showcases the alignment of the deployed components with the architectural specification. Section 3 presents technical details on the implementation of each component and the way its functionality is exposed/connected within the overall platform. Section 4 presents the user-facing application that exposes the platform to its end users. Finally, Section 5 summarises and proposes future steps for the continuation and further development of the platform.

2 TRACEMYFISH FINALISED ARCHITECTURAL SPECIFICATION

As the main technical constituents and the testing scenarios solidified in the course of the project thus far, the architectural design of the overall platform evolved to adapt to the more concrete needs of the TMF use cases and pilots, building on the initial conceptual design.

The updated architecture is depicted in the following figure.

Figure 1: TraceMyFish high-level architecture

The data management process is initialized by the association of a *product unit* (e.g., a parcel or batch) with a unique ID. The ID accompanies the unit and links to the collected and inferred information for the unit as measurements are collected in the designated points across the value chain. At that point, measurements are initially transferred at the Videometer Cloud. From there, they are transferred as-is to the TraceMyFish cloud storage. They are validated and pre-processed before being added to the data series used as input to the TraceMyFish models, which assess the status of the product based on the data points thus far.

Finally, data aggregates and predictive results are exposed to the user-facing applications. Each measurement is associated with the parcel, the timepoint of the measurement and the actor active in the specific step of the Value Chain.

The TraceMyFish platform is able to ingest data from different streams, including directly communicating sensors, mobile applications, web applications and cloud-based systems. Data Ingestion is carried out by the respective calls to the **TraceMyFish Data API**, accessed via the AAI mechanisms of the iFMS, integrated with the respective AAI mechanisms of the client application (e.g., the VideoMeter Lab software).

The data are sent in a tabular object format (CSV) to the Quantum platform to undergo further analysis by the Quantum Pipelines for Pre-processing and Analysis. Analytical results and responses to custom user queries are again carried out via calls to the TraceMyFish API, this time its data consumption but always under the AAI infrastructure of the platform, and in combination with the **Models API**, which controls the enactment and parameterisation of the TraceMyFish AI models. Data and Analysis Results are exposed via an Authorization-enabled REST API, in order to ensure controlled access to the data by the iFMS user-facing applications and

third-party tools in the future. The Data API is implemented in PHP, using the Laravel framework¹, while the Models API is implemented in Python.

¹ <https://laravel.com>

3 TECHNOLOGIES

3.1 DATA REPRESENTATION

The data exchange format used throughout the TraceMyFish Data Platform is the widely used JSON specification, as it is particularly suited for web applications and facilitates further extensions and connections with third-party and future applications.

3.2 COMMUNICATION APIS

The APIs providing controlled access to the data platform are implemented in PHP using the Laravel framework². The API entails calls for the following operations:

1. Register a device
2. Register a parcel and generate an ID for it
3. Submit data measurements for the parcel
4. Retrieve timeseries data for a parcel
5. Retrieve predictive results for a parcel at a timepoint
6. Retrieve accumulative results for an actor (all parcels associated with the specific actor)

3.3 PROCESSING AND ANALYTICS PIPELINE

The pre-processing components of the TraceMyFish iFMS are incorporated into an instantiation of the Quantum data platform. They are responsible for the preparation of the incoming data streams before further analysis is possible. On the one hand, the components deal with the identification and annotation/elimination of outlier measurements and identification of gaps in measurement timeseries. On the other hand, harmonization components are responsible for transforming the input data in the representation that will be used for ingesting them in the appropriate persistent storage mechanisms as described below. Communication between the pipeline components is implemented through the use of an Apache Kafka³ infrastructure for message passing via a message bus monitored by all components.

The AI Pipeline encapsulates all modules responsible for the analysis of the incoming data towards producing predictions and recommendations for assessing food condition and applying mitigative actions in case a hazard is identified. The modules are organised under a workflow that facilitates their re-training in timely intervals as more data and analyses become available, minimising the effort for training, validating and re-deploying the trained models. They are implemented as Python and R scripts and deployed as Docker containers integrated into the overall Quantum pipeline and its message bus.

3.4 PERSISTENT STORAGE

The data platform incorporates two persistent storage mechanisms, one for storing raw data as delivered by the TMF API and one for storing processed data and analytical results.

The first data store is a MongoDB⁴ deployment, to which the incoming data are deposited via the downstream API. A NoSQL database is used for storing the raw measurement timeseries as delivered by the sensing devices and the applications feeding data in the platform and exported by the pre-processing pipeline.

A ledger infrastructure based on the Hyperledger Fabric platform⁵ is used for installation-bound analytics and processed data, to ensure security and history immutability and preservation. For the purposes of the pilots, the ledger does not enforce a strict contract. This will be determined after the first round of pilots that will present more clearly the needs and verification requirements of each actor in the handled chains.

² <https://laravel.com/>

³ <https://kafka.apache.org>

⁴ <https://www.mongodb.com>

⁵ <https://www.hyperledger.org/use/fabric>

3.5 FRONTEND TECHNOLOGIES

The first version of the iFMS user interface is implemented as an RShiny⁶ application, in order to facilitate the integration with the outputs of the predictive components. The application uses the calls defined in the TraceMyFish API to consume directly or combine data towards producing the relevant visualizations and information to each end user type. Users at different steps of the value chain have different access rights, depending on their role in the chain. For the purpose of piloting the iFMs at its entirety, an administration account currently has access to all the collected and produced data, in order to assess the correctness and efficiency of the platform.

⁶ <https://shiny.rstudio.com>

4 TRACEMYFISH APP

The TraceMyFish web app is a prototype for the web interface of the TraceMyFish iFMS, allowing users to go submit and go through their data, as well as obtain predicted values for the metrics covered by the TraceMyFish AI models. For demonstration purposes, and as the ingested pilot data are openly available, the app does not require authentication, i.e. the authentication/authorisation part of the infrastructure is bypassed.

To use the app, the first step is to select the value chain relevant to the current user, from the setup panel at the left side of the screen.

Figure 2: TraceMyFish App - Fish Value Chain Selection

For all value chains, the user has the following options after they have specified their chain of interest:

- a. **View all data:** users are able to view all data points ingested for this value chain.

Figure 3: TraceMyFish App - View all data

- b. **Register sample:** users are able to manually add data points (measurements) in the chain for a new sample.

Figure 4: TraceMyFish App - Sample Registration

- c. **View sample history:** users are able to retrieve all data points for a specific sample.

Figure 5: TraceMyFish App - Sample History

- d. **Predict target variables:** users are able to retrieve the prediction results as generated by the relevant model, for each of the different chains and each different metric relevant to the chain.

Figure 6: TraceMyFish App - Target Variables per Fish Value Chain

They subsequently provide the sample for which they want to retrieve the predicted value, and the model prediction for the given sample and metric is displayed on the app’s main panel.

Figure 7: TraceMyFish App - Predictive Results

The TraceMyFish App is available via a permanent link⁷, and continuously informed by the latest version of the TraceMyFish AI models, as they are re-trained and re-evaluated when further data are ingested into the platform.

⁷ <https://scio-data-science.shinyapps.io/tracemyfish-shinyapp1/>

5 CONCLUSIONS

The report serves as an informative document presenting the communication points and technologies employed in the TraceMyFish iFMS Data Platform. As the backend infrastructure is generally stable, future work will focus on robustness and communication stability. An important next step for the iFMS as a product is the evolution of the TraceMyFish app to a product-level front-end, taking also into account stability factors, as well as the enablement of the authorisation mechanism and the incorporation of a pricing strategy for its usage. Additionally, UI/UX improvements are critical for leveraging the app and constituting it more user-friendly and more attractive to the targeted end users.